

Notes: System architecture of the PARTNER framework for adaptive reminiscence interaction. The system integrates multimodal sensing (facial expression, voice, motion) via a Sensor Hub, performs emotion estimation and adaptive dialogue planning using LLM modules, and dynamically presents personalized media through Pepper's tablet and audio interface. A closed-loop feedback mechanism enables real-time human-aware response modulation based on user engagement.

Fig. 1. System architecture of the PARTNER framework for adaptive reminiscence interaction.

PARTNER: A Multimodal Emotion-Aware Robot System for Personalized Reminiscence Exercise

Wenzheng Zhao, Ruth P. Lopez, Shu-Fen Wung, Kevin Berner, Fengpei Yuan

Background. Individuals with early-stage Alzheimer's disease (AD/ADRD) often experience social isolation and a lack of meaningful engagement. Reminiscence therapy, which uses personal media to evoke memories and encourage conversation, has shown promise in improving emotional well-being. However, consistently delivering these interactions in an emotionally responsive manner is challenging without the significant involvement of caregiver.

Purpose. As shown in Figure 1, In this project, we propose Personalized AI and Robotics to Nurture Engaging Reminiscence (PARTNER) system. This system uses the humanoid social robot, Pepper [1], to integrate multimodal emotion sensing and language generation, supporting personalized reminiscence conversations for older adults. The goal is to design an adaptive, personalized, and low-burden technology that complements human caregivers by promoting meaningful engagement, conversation and emotional connection for individuals with dementia in long-term care settings.

Methods. The PARTNER system consists of the humanoid robot (Pepper) and a web-based portal called "MemoryLane". Pepper is equipped with audio-visual sensing capabilities and a tablet interface. The MemoryLane cloud-hosted portal individuals with AD/ADRD and their caregivers (the primary users) to upload personalized media, such as photos. During interactions, the robot detects the user's emotions through facial and vocal cues using a local sensor hub, and responds using a GPT4o-based language model [2]. This response is modulated by a dialogue policy engine. The robot displays relevant media while adjusting its speech tone and content in real-time. Internal testing of the entire system pipeline was conducted to verify its responsiveness and the integration of multimodal sensing, media presentation, and LLM-guided conversation.

Results. We conducted an informal on-site demonstration and testing of the PARTNER system at the Sharon Adult Center, MA, involving two professional dementia care experts, who independently evaluated both the MemoryLane portal and the embodied reminiscence robot interface. Their qualitative feedback was highly positive, highlighting the system's potential to facilitate person-centered conversations and interactions with individuals with AD/ADRD. The experts provided specific suggestions for enhancing system responsiveness and user experience. These, included optimizing questions based on the 6Ms framework (Meaning, Motivation, etc.), improving the naturalness of the robot's physical gestures, dynamically adjusting the length and pacing of verbal outputs, improving the layout of the robotic tablet display for better visual clarity, and emphasizing the importance of cloud-based functionality for the caregiver portal. In particular, they recommended allowing family members or professional caregivers to pre-upload personalized memory materials, —such as photos or stories, —to the portal. This would enable better content preparation and management of content prior to the robot's interaction.

These internal evaluations, conducted in collaboration with dementia care experts affirmed both the system's usability and its relevance for future deployment scenarios, while also providing constructive feedback for system refinement and insights for real-world applications.

Discussion and Conclusion. The PARTNER system demonstrates the feasibility of delivering adaptive, emotionally aware, personalized reminiscence interactions through a closed-loop robot system. Initial internal testing indicates high system responsiveness and effective emotional modulation in response to input signals. While human-subject studies are planned, this preliminary system offers a promising direction for AI-assisted dementia care, where personalized and, engaging interactions can be delivered with minimal human effort.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The author would like to thank the developers of the system, Professor Fiona Yuan, and the faculty collaborators from the MGH Institute of Health Professions for their valuable guidance.

REFERENCES

- [1] A. K. Pandey and R. Gelin, "A mass-produced sociable humanoid robot: Pepper: The first machine of its kind," *IEEE Robotics & Automation Magazine*, vol. 25, no. 3, pp. 40–48, 2018.
- [2] OpenAI, "Gpt-4v(ision) system card," 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:263218031>